

NODES – Nord Ovest Digitale e Sostenibile

Report on the procedure developed for the preparation of waste extracts

SPOKE N 6 Primary Agroindustry

**Flagship project VINO
RM4 - Don't waste the waste**

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Glossary

	Definition
Hub Coordinator (HC)	The Hub Coordinator represents the single point of contact for the implementation of the innovation ecosystem towards the MUR. It carries out the management and coordination activities of the innovation ecosystem, receives the fundings, verifies, and transmits to the MUR the reporting of the activities carried out by the Spoke and their affiliates.
National Recovery and Resilience Plan (NRRP)	This document uses the Italian acronym for the NRRP, which is PNRR (Piano Nazionale della Ripresa e Resilienza)
Research Program Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the NODES project. The NODES will appoint the Research Program Manager. It refers to “Responsabile del Programma di Ricerca” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
NODES’ Research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spoke, with the aim to promote and support applied research on topics consistent with the Intelligent Specialization Strategy, with the guidelines of the 2021-2027 partnership agreement scheme, with regional operational plans and regional and national research and innovation priorities. Although NODES’ Spokes are concentrated on different themes, they will organize their activities and actions within a common framework – NODES’ Booster Methodology
Spoke Coordinator	The University in charge of coordinating the Spoke’s ecosystem. It refers to “Spoke” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”
Spoke Data Manager	The person who will be responsible for the monitoring and management of data generated at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Data Manager.
Spoke Partner	The entity associated to the Spoke Coordinator. It can be an Innovation Cluster, Competence Center, Research Center related to the Spoke’s ecosystem and contributes to achieve objectives and impact under the Spoke’ leadership and management. It refers to “soggetti affiliati” in the MUR’s Call of proposal for “Ecosistemi di Innovazione”.
Spoke Project manager	The person who will be responsible for the management, coordination and progress of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Project Manager.
Spoke research and innovation program	NODES’ Research and Innovation program is articulated in specific programs for each Spokes. The spoke will leverage a consolidated collaboration with leading private and public companies and will focus the applied research activity on technological domains and applications that can favour the integration of SMEs into new value chains.
Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager	The person who will be responsible for the overall scientific contents of the project at the Spoke level. The Spoke Coordinator will appoint the Spoke Scientific and Technical Manager.
Spoke Stakeholders Committee (SC)	Consultation structure formed by relevant stakeholders (Government, universities, companies, civil society, third sector, etc.)
Spoke Thematic	General target focus and domain of the Spoke research.
Spoke Topics	Specific areas/lines of development within the Spoke.
Spoke Work Package Leader	At the Spoke level, Work Packages (WPs) will be organized by WP leaders, who will be responsible for performance evaluation and reporting.
Flagship Project	Main research project at the Spoke level with the goal of prototyping, testing, and demonstrating the research activities towards higher TRLs.

Within the context of waste valorization, activities of RM4 recently focused on the set up of a green extraction procedure for pruning residues derived from the cultivation of *Olea europaea* L. To optimize the extraction process, a Design of Experiment (DoE) approach was adopted. To this purpose, both Microwave-Assisted Solvent Extraction (MAE) and Ultrasound-Assisted Solvent Extraction (UAE) were exploited, each offering clear economic and practical advantages, such as reduced extraction times with respect to conventional extraction techniques, minimal solvent usage and effectiveness in the protection of thermolabile compounds. Furthermore, these methods demonstrated high extraction efficiency, excellent reproducibility, and strong robustness.

A) Material and Methods

In this section chemicals (e.g. standards and solvents), instruments and methodologies used (e.g. for HPLC-UV analysis, MAE and UAE procedures, DPPH assay) are reported.

Plant material

One-year old lignified shoots of *Olea europaea* L. cultivar Matosso were collected from a 5-year-old plant at the "VALENTINI GERMANO" Ca' Albertini 2-Frazione Pizzofreddo - Santa Maria della Versa, Pavia. After collection, plant material was cleaned, cut and left to dry in a ventilated stove at 35°C until constant weight and then stored in a dark, dry place. Before extraction, plant material was grinded finely.

Chemicals

HPLC-grade solvents were supplied by Honeywell (Seelze, Germany), while analytical grade solvents were supplied by PanReac (Barcelona, Spain). Formic acid, 2,2-Diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) and Oleuropein were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Milan, Italy). Oasis® HLB 6 cc Vac cartridge were supplied by VWR (Milan, Italy).

Instruments and methods

HPLC-UV analysis

All analyses were carried out using a JASCO (Jasco Europe, Cremella, Italy) bench-top HPLC system, including a quaternary pump model PU-4180, autosampler model AS-4050 with a 5 µL loop installed on purpose, column thermostatic compartment model CO-4065, and an UV-Vis photodiode array detector model MD-4010. The system was fully operated by the JASCO ChromNAV software (version 2.04.03) operating in Microsoft Windows 7 Professional environment.

Extracts from *Olea europaea* L. were analyzed using a previously developed HPLC-UV method¹¹. Briefly, HPLC analyses were performed using a Kinetex C18 column (4.6 mm ID x 150 mm, particle size 2.6 µm, Phenomenex®, Torrance, California). The mobile phase consisted of water containing 0.1% (v/v) formic acid (A) and acetonitrile (B).

The elution was in gradient mode as follows: isocratic elution at 3% B for 3 min, from 3% to 30% of B in 18 min, from 30% to 65% of B in 5 min, up to 90% of B in 2 min. The column was reconditioned by eluting from 90% of B to 3% of B in 3 min, followed by a final isocratic elution at the initial conditions (3% of B) for 7 min. The analyses were performed at 25°C and at a flow rate of 0.7 mL min⁻¹. The injection volume of each sample was 3 µL. The UV-visible absorbance was recorded from 190 to 600 nm, and the quantification of oleuropein was performed at 230 nm applying the external standard method. To this aim a six-points calibration curve, each replicated three times, in the range of 1000 – 10 µg mL⁻¹ was built. Specificity and linearity were evaluated according to the ICH Q2 (R2). The calibration curve exhibited excellent linearity [$y = (4,039,798 \pm 75,935.9)x + (124,481 \pm 47,244.3)$; $R^2 = 0.9986$] over the concentration range the quantification limits, QL, was assessed using the following formulas:

$$QL = 5 \frac{\sigma}{S}$$

Where σ is the standard error of the y-intercept, and S is the mean slope of the calibration curve. The QL was established at 60 µg mL⁻¹,

Repeatability was verified by performing 10 determinations at the oleuropein test concentration of 0.5 mg mL⁻¹ (RSD = 1.01% for peak area).

Extraction of Olea europaea pruning residues

Two extraction techniques, microwave-assisted solvent extraction (MAE) and ultrasound-assisted solvent extraction (UAE), were employed to prepare extracts from *Olea europaea* L. pruning residues. Two different responses, as measured by the total amount of oleuropein (Y1) and free radical scavenging activity (% FRS, Y2), of the extracts were studied. Y1 was computed by HPLC analysis using the external calibration curve method and expressed as mg of metabolite per g of dry matrix weight (DW); Y2 was determined through DPPH assay (extract single-dose determination).

The experimental plan consisted of three continuous factors varying over two levels (X_1, X_2, X_3) and one qualitative factor varying over three levels (the starting biomass). Factor X_1 was the temperature (studied from 40 to 90°C for MAE and from 30 to 80°C for UAE), X_2 represented the number of extraction cycles (from 1 to 3 cycles), and X_3 was the solvent composition (ethanol-to-water volume ratio, from 20:80 to 80:20). The sample matrix was the qualitative factor varying

¹¹ Mir-Cerdà, Aina, Mercè Granados, Javier Saurina, and Sonia Sentellas. 2024. 'Olive Tree Leaves as a Great Source of Phenolic Compounds: Comprehensive Profiling of NaDES Extracts'. *Food Chemistry* 456:140042. doi:10.1016/j.foodchem.2024.140042.

from branch (dummy factors coding $X_4 = 1$ and $X_5 = 0$), to leaves ($X_4 = 0$ and $X_5 = 1$), to pruning waste ($X_4 = X_5 = 0$), defined as a mixture of branches and leaves without undergoing any separation.

The exhaustive factorial plan thus counted to a list of 24 experiments ($2^3 \cdot 3 = 24$). A D-optimal design was employed to identify the optimal list of experiments. Three additional independent trials were added to the experimental plan to test the model's validity (experiments #11, 12, and 13). The experimental plan is described in Tables 1 and 2 for MAE and UAE, respectively.

Specific settings of the MAE and UAE parameters are described below:

- MAE extraction was carried out using a power of 80 Watts for the experiment at 90°C, 25 Watts for all experiments at 40°C, and 79 Watts for the experiment at 65 °C; a maximum pressure of 120 PSI; a ramp time of 2 min, and an extraction time of 5 minutes for each cycle under magnetic stirring.

- UAE extraction was carried out using a working frequency of 37 kHz and an electric power output of 250 W for experiments at 30°C, 80 kHz and an electric power output of 450 W for experiments at 80°C, and 55Hz and 350 W for experiments at 55°C. Each cycle lasted 10 min.

Other parameters were kept constant for both the extraction methods, including the biomass/solvent ratio at 1/50 g mL⁻¹ (i.e., 250 mg of the biomass extracted with 12.5 mL of solvent) and the operator. After each extraction, the mixture was allowed to cool to room temperature and filtered using vacuum filtration with a Büchner funnel. To wash the filter, 3 mL of solvent was applied, varying its composition according to the experimental plan. After filtration, the solvents were removed under reduced pressure and samples were dried until they reached a constant weight.

Table 1 MAE ten-experiment D-optimal experimental plan and three validation experiments (Exp#11-13).

Exp#	X_1	X_2	X_3	$X_4; X_5$	X_1	X_2	X_3	X_4	X_5	Y_1	Y_2
	Temperature	Cycles	Solvent Composition	matrix	Temperature	Cycles	Solvent Composition	Branches	Leaves	Amount of oleuropein ^a (mg g ⁻¹ DW)	%FRS ^b
1	90	1	20/80	Branches	1	-1	-1	1	0	73.2	53.3
2	40	3	20/80	Branches	-1	1	-1	1	0	48.9	47.3
3	40	1	80/20	Branches	-1	-1	1	1	0	23.0	68.9
4	90	3	80/20	Branches	1	1	1	1	0	39.5	44.7
5	90	1	20/80	Leaves	1	-1	-1	0	1	88.3	72.2
6	40	3	20/80	Leaves	-1	1	-1	0	1	76.3	69.3
7	40	1	20/80	Pruning waste	-1	-1	-1	0	0	51.2	53.6
8	90	3	20/80	Pruning waste	1	1	-1	0	0	68.8	56.4
9	90	1	80/20	Pruning waste	1	-1	1	0	0	59.4	63.7
10	40	3	80/20	Pruning waste	-1	1	1	0	0	57.6	49.2
Validation trials											
11	65	2	50/50	Pruning waste	0	0	0	0	0	68.2	56.1
12	65	2	50/50	Pruning waste	0	0	0	0	0	76.8	50.8
13	65	2	50/50	Pruning waste	0	0	0	0	0	66.0	50.3

Oleuropein was quantified in the extract by UHPLC-UV/PDA through calibration curves after chlorophyll removal

^b determined through DPPH assay at a single dose (0.4 mg mL⁻¹ in methanol)

Table 2 UAE ten-experiment D-optimal experimental plan and three validation experiments (Exp#11-13).

Exp #	X ₁ Temperature	X ₂ Cycles	X ₃ Solvent Compositio n	X ₄ ; X ₅ matrix	X ₁ Temperature	X ₂ Cycles	X ₃ Solvent Compositio n	X ₄ Branches	X ₅ Leaves	Y ₁ Amount of Oleuropein ^a (mg g ⁻¹ DW)	Y ₂ %FRS ^b
1	80	1	20/80	Branches	1	-1	-1	1	0	35.3	47.0
2	30	3	20/80	Branches	-1	1	-1	1	0	28.0	51.4
3	30	1	80/20	Branches	-1	-1	1	1	0	32.1	53.3
4	80	3	80/20	Branches	1	1	1	1	0	36.6	46.8
5	80	1	20/80	Leaves	1	-1	-1	0	1	54.3	62.4
6	30	3	20/80	Leaves	-1	1	-1	0	1	61.8	56.3
7	30	1	20/80	Pruning waste	-1	-1	-1	0	0	29.6	51.6
8	80	3	20/80	Pruning waste	1	1	-1	0	0	59.6	54.8
9	80	1	80/20	Pruning waste	1	-1	1	0	0	62.7	61.0
10	30	3	80/20	Pruning waste	-1	1	1	0	0	69.0	56.0
Validation trials											
11	55	2	50/50	Pruning waste	0	0	0	0	0	45.6	55.8
12	55	2	50/50	Pruning waste	0	0	0	0	0	65.6	54.9
13	55	2	50/50	Pruning waste	0	0	0	0	0	70.9	50.0

^a Oleuropein was quantified in the extract by UHPLC-UV/PDA through calibration curves after chlorophyll removal

^b determined through DPPH assay at a single dose (0.4 mg mL⁻¹ in methanol)

Chlorophyll removal through SPE

Before determining responses Y1 and Y2, chlorophylls were removed from all the extracts via a solid phase extraction (SPE) method recently developed by us, with slight modifications. Briefly, the cartridges Waters OASIS HLB 1cc were mounted on the manifold and conditioned with 1 mL of methanol. 1 mL of each extract previously dissolved in methanol ($c = 20 \text{ mg mL}^{-1}$) was loaded into cartridges, the vacuum was applied and the cartridge washed with 1 mL of 50% MeOH and 50% water to complete sample elution. At the end the solvent was evaporated under reduced pressure to obtain the purified extracts, while the cartridge was washed with dichloromethane and reactivated with MeOH for future uses.

DPPH free radical scavenging activity

Extracts prepared according to the D-optimal experimental plan, after chlorophyll removal, were tested by the DPPH assay using a multi-well plate, according to Brand-Williams et al., with slight modifications. Briefly, for each extract a stock solution was prepared at a concentration of 0.4 mg mL^{-1} in methanol [63]. Then sample, blank and control solutions were prepared as follows: for sample solution $10 \mu\text{L}$ of the extract stock solution were mixed with $190 \mu\text{L}$ of DPPH methanolic solution (0.15 mM); for blank solution $190 \mu\text{L}$ of methanol were mixed with $10 \mu\text{L}$ of the extract stock solution; for control solution $190 \mu\text{L}$ of DPPH methanolic solution (0.15 mM) were mixed with $10 \mu\text{L}$ of methanol. The plate was incubated in the dark at room temperature for 30 minutes, and then the absorbance was measured at 515 nm using a microplate reader. The percentage of free radical scavenging activity was calculated using the following formula:

$$\%FRS = 100 \times \frac{A_{ctrl} - (A_{sample} - A_{blank})}{A_{ctrl}}$$

Where % FRS is the free radical scavenging activity percent, A_{ctrl} is the absorbance of the control, A_{sample} is the raw data reading of the sample, and A_{blank} is the absorbance of the blank.

Statistical analysis

All data were analyzed using Microsoft Excel for Windows 365 MSO (Version 18.2002.1101.0), CAT (Chemometric Agile Tool, by Leardi, C. Melzi, G. Polotti), freely downloadable from <http://gruppochemiometria.it/index.php/software>, developed in R for Microsoft Windows (version 3.2.3, Copyright 2014) and GraphPad Prism 8.0 (GraphPad Software Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). The Shapiro–Wilk and Bartlett Tests were used to establish the normality of the parameters. Then, population mean values comparisons were carried out using a one-way ANOVA, followed by Bonferroni's post hoc test for multiple comparisons. Statistical significance was evaluated at a 95% confidence interval, and the differences were considered statistically significant for $p < 0.05$ (*), $p < 0.01$ (**), and $p < 0.001$ (***)).

B) Extraction procedure set-up.

In this section the set-up of a green extraction procedure of *Olea Europaea* L. pruning residues is reported

To set up a green extraction procedure for pruning wood from *Olea europaea* L both ultrasound and microwave-assisted extraction methodologies were exploited, each offering clear economic and practical advantages with respect to conventional extraction techniques. To this aim, a Design of Experiment (DoE) approach, specifically a D-Optimal model, was adopted.

Preliminary studies were first conducted to identify the experimental variables to be included in the DoE experimental plan and those to be kept constant throughout the entire experiment (e.g. plant material/solvent ratio, extraction time). Then, a DoE experimental extraction plan was designed applying a D-optimal model, which allowed us to simultaneously compare the effect of three factors, namely temperature, number of cycles and solvent composition on three different plant matrices: branches leaves and their combination. In total only 13 experiments were performed. All other parameters (e.g., amount of dried plant material, volume of solvent, type of vessel), including the operator, were kept constant.

The extraction plan was designed to study two responses, namely amount of Oleuropein (Y_1) determined through HPLC analysis and % scavenging activity (Y_2). For each experiment, once the extraction was completed, the mixture was filtered through a Büchner funnel. To wash the filter, 3 mL of solvent was applied, varying in composition according to the experimental plan. The eluate was then evaporated to dryness, and the crude extract was subjected to chlorophyll removal through solid phase extraction before determining the three responses Y_1 and Y_2 .

Statistical analysis of the results (Tables 1 and 2) pointed out that MAE is the best extraction method, i) giving better results associated with oleuropein extraction yield and %FRS comparable to that of UAE, and ii) requiring half the extraction time of UAE. Experimental conditions involving an 80:20 ethanol/water extraction solvent, one 5-minute microwave cycle at 40°C with a power of 25 W, and a 1:50 plant material-to-solvent ratio (e.g. 250 mg of plant material extracted using 12.5 mL of solvent). were identified as optimal for the biomasses considered (Table 3)

Table 3. Optimized MAE conditions

material/solvent ratio (mg/mL)	MAE conditions			
	Temperature	Number of cycles	Cycle time	Solvent composition (v/v)
1/50	40°C	1	5min	80%Etanol 20% H ₂ O